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Effect of deposition time on structure of silver nanoparticles embedded in diamond-like carbon matrix made by RF-PECVD method

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Abstract

Silver nanoparticles embedded in DLC matrix, were prepared by co-deposition of RF-Sputtering and RF-PECVD method from acetylene gas and silver target. The RF power and initial pressure of chamber were fixed. Variations of morphology, optical and electrical properties of these films over time were investigated.

Keywords: Optical and electrical properties, RF-PECVD, Silver nanoparticles.